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INNOVATIVE PRINCIPLES IN DESIGNING THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS BASED ON STEAM EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY

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***Abstract:** The methods and means of conveying to pedagogues that the formation of STEAM teaching technology in preschool educational organizations is of great importance, the content, forms and ways of using the means of forming STEAM teaching technology in preschool educational organizations are discussed.*

***Basic concepts:** Innovation, technology, preschool education, pedagogical process, design, STEAM, technology, education, concept, development, center, competence.*

It is an honorable task for every pedagogue to carefully lead the young generation up the ladder of development. We just need to understand the characteristics of this movement and support children in time, create suitable conditions for their growth. In this regard, the process of preschool education is important. Today, innovations aimed at updating preschool education both in form and content require all pedagogues to approach child education and his readiness for education based on the requirements of the time. Dynamically developing technologies are introduced in all spheres of human activity. Future professionals will need comprehensive education and knowledge from various fields of technology, science and engineering.

STEAM technology, unlike education, ensures that knowledge is not isolated, but mutually proportional. The child develops the skills of non-standard thinking, finding several solutions to the problem and creativity, which will be very useful in his future work. Play is the leading activity in preschool education, but according to STEAM technology researchers, children's leading activity is experience. With the help of toys, children learn to read, measure, level, count, paint, communicate and acquire team skills. This will help them acquire the necessary mathematical, philological and engineering, artistic skills.

STEAM educational technology helps children develop the following important characteristics and skills: a comprehensive understanding of problems understanding, creative thinking, engineering approach, critical thinking, understanding and application of scientific methods, understanding design principles.

Today, STEAM education is developing as one of the main trends in the world and is based on the integration of five areas into a single educational scheme in the application of the practical approach. The conditions of such education are its continuity and the development of children's ability to communicate in groups, where they collect and exchange ideas. Therefore, modules for the development of logical thinking such as Lego-technologies, children's research are included in the basic educational program.

Undoubtedly, one of the main elements of today's modern education system is new, i.e., innovative pedagogical technologies. Conducting or organizing lesson processes through these pedagogical technologies serves to open a great way for both free and new thinking of students. Today's high development of science, technology, technology and production automatically puts new social demands on the agenda. Among these social requirements, the society, moreover, the force that moves the development of industries on its basis - the training of qualified personnel and the improvement of the system aimed at this goal are important. Although the need for training of qualified personnel arose in the early stages of the development of the industrial sector, when production enterprises appeared, it still does not lose its

relevance. The main reasons for this are the emergence of new directions, specializations, the need to train personnel in accordance with the social, economic and cultural development of society, the need to consistently improve the professional knowledge, skills and skills of specialists in a changing, fast-paced era, as well as the increased demand to withstand strong competition in the labor market as a specialist.

The current educational development has brought a new direction - innovative pedagogy to the field. The term "innovative pedagogy" and related research appeared in Western Europe and the United States in the 60s. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by the American innovator E. Rogers. He studies the classification of categories (types) of the participants of the innovation process, their attitude to the innovation, their readiness to perceive it.

Pedagogical technology — studies the problems of applying modern pedagogical technologies in the process of education and training, improving the effectiveness of the process of education and training based on the technological approach.

Turning to the dictionary meaning of the word technology, this word is derived from the Greek words "tehnos" - skill, art "logos" - teaching, science. It follows that the word technology is added to other terms and fulfills the tasks of developing this field and improving its skills. In general, technology is an objective process that has prepared the stage of educational evolution to solve qualitatively new issues. New technologies have opened up great educational opportunities. The qualitative changes that are taking place indicate that, in the usual explanation, the processes of "teaching" are teachers began to go beyond the limits of professional capabilities. The new technical, informational, printed, auditory and exhibition tools that have appeared in their own way introduce many innovations to the educational process with new methods and remain an inseparable part of it. However, the uniqueness of the pedagogical technological process, its priority over the traditional forms, and methods of real solution to the problems of modern education have not yet been fully studied. Foreign and Uzbek authors write a lot about it. But everyone believes that pedagogical technologies will have priority in the future.

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